

LITERARY REVIEW OF AYURVEDA IN MANAGEMENT OF VATASHTHILA**Dr. Satinderpal Singh*¹, Dr. Ranjit Singh Manhas², Dr. Bhoomi Soni³**¹PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.²Professor and H.O.D, Department of Shalya Tantra, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Shalya Tantra, Quadra Institute of Ayurveda, Roorkee, Haridwar, Uttarakhand, India.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Satinderpal Singh**

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ABSTRACT

Vatashthila is one of the types of *Mutraghata* in which there is decreased urine flow due to obstruction in urinary passage. Inappropriate *Ahaara-Vihaara*, excessive excursion, stress and other circumstances increase *Vata Dosha*, particularly *Apaan Vata* which leads to formation of *Asthilavat Ghan*, *Unnat Granthi* between urinary bladder and rectum which causes *Vin Mutra Anil Sangha*, *Adhmaana*, *Vedana in Basti Pradesh*. In essence, BPH is an enlarged prostate gland in which benign prostate hyperplasia of prostate gland occurs, which is non-cancerous and age related. Particularly hormonal imbalances from androgens cause prostate growth. Unable to empty the bladder, dribbling, urgency, hesitancy, frequency, nocturia etc lower urinary tract symptoms (LUTS) which hampers the quality of life of patient. Due to resemblance in symptoms as well as anatomical consideration *Vatashthila* bears a close resemblance with BPH. In modern medicine, BPH is managed through oral medications aimed at reducing prostate size and relaxing smooth muscles, alongside surgical interventions such as transurethral resection of the prostate (TURP) or prostatectomy for severe cases. However, these treatments carry risks and may not be suitable for all elderly patients. In *Ayurveda*, the approach to treating *Vatashthila* involves addressing the root cause by normalizing *Apana Vayu* and clearing the obstructed channels through therapies like *Srotoshodhan* (cleansing of channels), *Vatanuloman* (balancing *Vata*), *Lekhana* (scrapping) and *Rasayana* (rejuvenation therapies). Ayurvedic therapies aim not only to alleviate symptoms but also to improve overall health and function of the affected tissues and organs, thereby enhancing the patient's quality of life.

KEYWORDS: *Vatashthila*, Benign Prostate Hyperplasia, *Vata dosha*.**➤ INTRODUCTION**

Vatashthila is a type of *Mutraghata* in which Aggravated *Vata Dosha* leads to formation of a glandular firm swelling like an *Asthila* which enlarges upward (all around) and obstruct the external orifice (prostatic urethra) which leads to obstruction of urine.^[2] In contemporary science *Vatashthila* resembles benign prostate hyperplasia. Benign prostatic hyperplasia is an enlargement of prostate, which is non-malignant.^[3] commonly occurring in men over the age of 50, with higher prevalence between 60 and 70 years. This condition involves both the glandular epithelium and the surrounding connective tissue stroma, leading to various urinary symptoms as the enlarged prostate compresses the urethra.

Acharya Sushruta explained *Vatashthila* as a condition characterized by the presence of *Apaan Vayu* in the area between the rectum (*Shakrinmarga*) and the urinary bladder (*Basti*). This results in a hard, immobile swelling that resembles a stone and obstructs the passage of stool, urine, and flatus (*Vida-Mutra-anil Sanga*) leading to bladder distension due to urine retention and cause severe suprapubic pain.^[4]

Vatashthila presents with symptoms such as urine retention, incomplete voiding, dribbling, and frequent micturition, often accompanied by straining during urination. These symptoms align with the characteristics of Lower Urinary Tract Symptoms (LUTS).

➤ MATERIAL AND METHODS

All data for this study is collected from ayurvedic literature viz. *Laghutrayi* and *Bruhatrayi* and from some published articles related to *Vatashthila*.

➤ NIDANA

There are no specific *Nidana* for *Vatashthila*, but those factors which are responsible for *Mutrakriccha* and *Mutraghata* and which hampers *Vata Dosha* can be taken into account for *Vatashthila* also.

1. *Vataprakopaka ahara- vihara*
2. *Vegaavidharan*
3. *katu-tikta ahara sewan*
4. *Adhyashan*
5. *Ajeernashana*
6. Excessive physical exertion
7. Rough food and wine
8. Riding on a fast moving vehicle.

➤ SAMPRAPTI^[5]

➤ LAKSHANAS^[6]

1. Obstruction of urine
 2. Flatulence
 3. Distension of bladder
- Pain in hypogastric region

➤ **CHIKITSA:** The management of *Vatashthila* in Ayurveda emphasizes a holistic approach, incorporating both "*Antahparimarjana*" (internal cleansing) and "*Bahirparimarjana*" (external cleansing).

The approach towards the treatment of disease is completed initially from *Nidana Parivarjana* to *Pathya-Apathya*. The common *Chikitsa sutra* for *Mutraghata* is use of drugs in the form of *Kashaya*, *Kalka*, *Sarpi*, *Bhakshya*, *Avleha*, *Payas*, *Kshara*, *Madya*, *Asava*, *Swedana*, *Basti*, *Uttara Basti* and formulation told in

context of *Ashmaree*, *Udavarta* are useful for managing *Mutraghata*.^[7]

The different *Yogas* which are mentioned by different *Acharya* in context to *Mutraghata* are as below.

Swarasa – *Nidigdihikadi* (B.P & Su.), *Amalaki* (Su), *Elayukta Dhatri* (A.S & Su.), *Nilutpaladi* (Ch), *Kantakari* (A.S & A.H), *Duralabha* (A.S & B.P) Etc.

Kalka – *Ervaru* (Su. & A.S.), *Mustaadi* (Su.), *Abhyaadi* (Su.), *Draksha* (Su. & A.S.), *Baladi* (Su.), *Shigrumoola* (Ch.), *Trapushaadi* (A.S.), *Simhyadi* (A.S.), *Moorvadi* (A.S.), *Sasaindhava Triphala* (A.S.), *Pasanabedadi* (A.H.), Etc.

Kwath – *Devadarvyadi* (A.H.), *Shatavaryadi* (Ch.), *Haritakyadi* (A.S. & Sha.), *Shringashtaka* (Ch. & A.S.), *Trinapanchamoolaadi* (A.S. & B.P.), *Kaandekshurakamoola* (A.S.), *Dhavadi* (A.S.), *Pashanabhedadi* (A.S.), *Gokshura* (Sha. & B.P.), *Naladi* (B.P. & Y.R.), *Vasa* (B.P.) Etc.

Choorna – *Vyoshadi*, *Ela*, *Pravala*, *Pashanabhedadi* (Ch.), *Pippalee*, *Surasa*, *Bibheetaka* (A.S.), *Hingvaadi Choorna* (Sha.), *Asdabhadradi Choorna* (B.P.), *Chandana* (B.P.), *ksheeradi Choorna* (Y.R.), *Khadir Beej Choorna*(Chkrdata)

Vati / Gutika – *Chandraprabha Vati*, *Gokshuradi Guggulu* (Sha.)

Ksheerpaka – *Kakolyadi*(Su), *Trikantakadi* (B.P. & Y.R).

Sneha (Ghrita) Kalpana – *Mootrarakta Yonidoshahara Ghrita*, *Bala Ghrita*, *Mahabala Ghrita*, (Su.); *Punarnavadi Mishraka Sneha*, *Pashanabhedadi Ghrita*, *Shwadanstra Ghrita*, *Sthiraadi Ghrita*, (Ch.); *Dashamooladi Ghrita*, *Tilvaka Ghrita* (A.S.); *Changeri Ghrita*, *Dhatuadi Taila*, *Tilvaka Ghrita* (Sha.); *Vidaari Ghrita*, *Bhadravaha Ghrita*, *Dhanyaka-Gokshura Ghrita* (B.P.).

Panayoga – *Punarnavadi* (Ch.)

Sandhana Kalpana – *Suraa* (Su.), *Nigada Madya*, *Madhukasava* (Ch.), *Tilaadi Kshara Yukta Sura* (A.S.).

Upanaha – *Punarnavadi* (Ch).

Yavagu – *Gokshurakantakari Siddha* (A.S).

Basti – *Dashamooladi Taila*, *Bilwadi Taila*, *Tila Taila*, *Shatavaryadi* (A.S.)

➤ PATHYA AND APATHYA^[8]

The most important and the most neglected aspect of the treatment is not following *Pathya* and *Apathya*. Diet plays a pivotal role in enhancing the efficacy of herbal medicines and treatments.

Pathyapathya for managing the disease *Mutraghata* is briefly described in the texts as follows.

Pathya in Mutraghata:- *Abhyanga, Swedan, Virechana, Basti, Avagaha- Sweda, Uttar Basti, Puratana Mamsa, Madya* made by *Dhanva, Takra, Purana Kushamand Phala, Patola, Ervaru, Kharjura, Narikela, Purana Shali, Yava*, etc. are all *Pathya* to the patients of *vatasthila*. By incorporating these dietary practices, individuals with *Vatasthila* can experience a reduction in symptoms and a better overall balance of Vata.

Apathya in Mutraghata:- *Virudha Anna, Ahara* which are *Ruksha, VIDAHEE, Vishtambhi & Vyavayee, Vegadharana, Vamana, Mutravegavarodha* etc. are *Apathya* as they contribute to vitiate *Vata dosha* and worsens the condition of urine retention as well as obstructs the flow of urine.

➤ DISCUSSION

Main aim in treating *vatasthila* is *Srotoshodhan* (cleansing of channels), *Vatanuloman* (balancing Vata), *Lekhana*(scrapping) which helps in reducing the size of prostate gland and improves the symptoms of *vatasthila*. The drugs mentioned above from ayurvedic texts have *Srotoshodhan, Vatanuloman, Lekhana* and *Rasayana* properties.

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